

Reporting relevance, availability, and needs of quality information in Earth System Science Data

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Executive Summary

Most Earth System Science (ESS) research projects are data driven and/or produce data sets as main results. Data quality is an essential criterion to evaluate a dataset's fitness for use, describing common characteristics of data from a methodological point of view. The survey gathers information from both a data consumer and producer perspective to better understand the relevance, availability, and needs of quality information on several levels of details. The survey was published during summer 2021.

This guide presents a brief summary of responses structured along the survey sections on (I) background information and (II) relevance and information needs regarding (a) data quality, (b) provenance, and (c) related visualizations.

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Background information

Data management has become an integral part of Earth System Sciences (ESS) research projects, fostering efficient, collaborative, long-term data-driven research. Ensuring access to quality assured data and metadata is of paramount importance in the data life cycle (see Figure 1) as quality information is a fundamental characteristic of data and provides the basis to determine fitness for use. It plays a major role in ESS, because earth observations, e.g. physical or chemical processes, are measured once, and the measured data is reused multiple times. For this reason, a meaningful description of data quality is essential.

The survey was developed within the GeoKur project. Within the project, we aim to support the curation and quality assurance of ESS data. The developments include concepts, best practices and tools to support Research Data Management for the discovery, reuse, and collaboration across-domain research including heterogeneous data sources. The requirement analysis for the tools includes high efforts in gathering meta information, in particular quality and provenance information, for potential analysis inputs.

Figure 1: Research Data Lifecycle (<https://www.gfbio.org/training/materials/data-lifecycle/plan>)

Purpose

In the survey, we aim to better understanding the relevance, availability, and needs of quality information on several levels of details from both a data consumer and producer perspective. The overarching goal is to integrate quality aspects in each phase of the life cycle, including developing proper metadata schemas as well as tools for tracking or visualization of quality information.

Structure

The survey is mainly structured around the data quality elements of ISO 19157 - Geographic information – Data quality addressing availability and needs on several levels of details. However, provenance information are strongly related to data quality, being key to understand data quality of a product with respect to its development, and are therefore included.

Table 1: Survey structure including sections and number of questions¹

Background information	8 [1 mandatory]
Relevance and Information needs	18 [2 mandatory]
Visualization	7 [no mandatory]

¹ Some of the questions are either producer- or consumer-specific, addressing information provision resp. needs.

Survey Results

Nowadays, Interest in and relevance of quality information is high, because sustainable and user-friendly approaches for data quality tracking, managing and visualizing are often lacking. The online survey was send to project partners and diverse established networks, like the ESIP Information Quality Cluster² or the Association of Geographic Information Laboratories in Europe (AGILE)³. 85 Participants started filling out the survey. However, only about 30 participants filled out section 1 on background information and about 10 participants filled out the complete questionnaire.

Section Background and research focus

B1. Which of the following options best describes your profession?

B2. In which country is your organization based?

² https://wiki.esipfed.org/Information_Quality

³ <https://agile-online.org/>

B3. Which is your main target audience?

B4. Which of the following options best describes your role regarding your data-driven work in earth system sciences?

B5. What is your domain?

B6. Are you involved in a specific community (e.g. NFDI, Agrovoc, RDA, eLTER)? Please specify.

- American Geophysical Union
- American Meteorological Society
- bitkom AK Open Data
- eLTER
- ESIP
- FAIRsFAIR
- Global land programme
- IEEM
- LULUC
- NFDI
- RDA

B7. What are your main research applications of your data-driven work? Please describe shortly.

- Formerly investigation of climate change. Now the publication of climate data .
- Physical oceanography
- The research I work on directly contributes to response strategies for climate change education, adaptation, and mitigation
- human-environment interactions
- Urban area analysis. Applications in land use modeling, assessment of environmental conditions, transportation planning
- geovisualization, map making
- Habitat and biodiversity conservation
- Visualization, Analytics and map production
- Find spatio-temporal patterns in multivariate data set
- Decadal variability
- remote sensing
- overlay analyses of different spatial data sets, derived from remote sensing and census data
- Climate change, soil carbon, vegetation change
- Numerical modeling, time series
- Identifying Land use change drivers and quantifying (potential) impacts.
- Soil function evaluation
- Reuse of atmospheric / climate model data for fundamental research like model development or evaluation of model performance through comparison to observations (i.e. satellite data or merged data products available on a grid). Global as well as regional data are used. Time and spatial resolution also varies.
- Assessing global food security, global impacts of climate change on agriculture
- Characterizing urban areas
- My research is on food and nutrition security in developing countries. We mainly use earth system science data to conduct research, technical assistance, and policy communications activities on a broad-range of economic development and poverty reduction issues related to improving food security and reducing malnutrition in an environmentally sustainable manner.
- We uncover the environmental implications of economic investments and provide guidance to government on courses of action to improve the environment in their countries.
- Land use sustainability

B8. What are main topic categories (e.g. yield, precipitation) frequently / typically used (data consumer) or provided (data producer)? Please list 1-3 categories.

First mentioned category:

- Wind
- ocean salinity
- Climate variables/variability
- Locations of human population
- land use
- climate
- land cover
- topographic information
- Ddd
- concentrations
- Sea ice data/daily and monthly/NSIDC (Snow and Ice Data Center) & ERA-5
- vegetation structure
- migration
- Temperature
- atmospheric temperatures over land (paleo through present)
- Yield
- soil properties
- soil parameters
- precipitation
- Elevation
- Climate
- Urban footprint / height / volume
- crop areas and yields, annually or even seasonally, both data consumer and producer
- Land Use and Land Use Change
- land use

Second mentioned category

- Precipitation
- ocean variability
- Climate regions
- Disasters
- building's height
- economic
- species presence
- relief
- Ddd
- precipitation
- Temperature and precipitation/daily and monthly/NCEI (NOAA National Centers for Environmental Information)
- forest inventory
- land degradation
- Precipitation
- erosion rates
- Climate (precipitation, temperature)
- aquifer properties
- DEM
- air temperature and humidity (3D)
- Thermal hotspots and fire activity

- Agricultural yield/production
- Scenario outcomes
- Livestock density, annually, both data consumer and producer
- Sand, Silt, Clay
- supply chains

Third category

- Air Pressure
- ocean circulation
- Public sectors
- Vulnerable populations
- ambient temperature
- transportation
- soil types
- lbsn
- Ddd
- discharge
- Global sea winds or surface temperature/monthly/NCEI & various projects - cruise and field data
- climate
- Vegetation
- precipitation for as far back in time as possible
- Consumption
- precipitation
- wind (3D)
- Weather radar
- Farm size
- Land system maps
- precipitation, daily, data consumer
- Soil depth
- household surveys

Section Relevance and information needs

Remark: Questions with a response of less than three participants are not included.

Data quality information

A1. How often is information about the quality element available (consumer) or provided (producer)?

A2. If you don't provide information about a certain quality element, please specify why.

A3. If information for positional accuracy is available, where do you obtain (consumer) or provide (producer) this information?

A4. If information about a quality element is available, how would you describe the accessibility of the information?

A5. Which source of information would you prefer for the given quality elements?

A6. Are the provided information structured using a standard (e.g. ISO 19157, Data Quality Vocabulary)?

If answered with yes: The specific standards Climate forecast and ISO 19115-1 were listed.

A9. Which level of detail do you prefer for the given quality elements?

A11. How important would you rate the access to training data used to derive the given quality elements and to its quality?

A12. Regardless of the availability, how useful are the given quality elements for evaluating a dataset's fitness for use for your application?

A15. What other aspects do you consider to evaluate the fitness for use of datasets?

Provenance

A1. How often is information about provenance available (consumer) or provided (producer)?

A3. If information for provenance is available, where do you obtain (consumer) or provide (producer) it?

A4. If information about provenance is available, how would you describe the accessibility?

Visualization

V1. How useful are linked provenance and quality information to evaluate the fitness for use of datasets for your application?

V2. What type of presentation do you prefer to visualize quality parameters?

V3. Do you use or need quality information for interim results of data products that you work with?

V7. How useful are linked provenance and quality information to visualize the quality of your data?

Removed questions

A7. Which metric (among some alternatives) do you usually use to report the given quality elements?

A8. Which metric would you like to promote as standard for deriving the given quality elements (e.g. omission rate)?

A10. Do you usually report training data and their spatial distribution?

A13. What other data quality elements and/or metadata would be useful for you to evaluate the fitness for use of datasets for your application (e.g. spatial, temporal or thematic resolution)?

A14. What other data quality elements and/or metadata do you typically provide?

A16. How do you evaluate the fitness for use of datasets? Please comment your selected answer if necessary.

A17. Do you have any other comments regarding data quality information?

V4. Would it be possible to generate quality information for interim results of data products?